

COMPOSITE CLASSIFIER MODEL BASED ON EXTREME GRADIENT BOOSTING FOR EARLY DETECTION OF CERVICAL CANCER

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ABSTRACT

Over the past few decades, cervical cancer has become one of the most common health issues affecting women worldwide, particularly in developing countries. Cervical cancer is a type of cancer that starts in the cervix, and it usually begins in the cells on the surface of the cervix. It has no noticeable signs when it first appears and can be deadly. However, if detected at an early stage, cervical cancer is treatable and curable. The high increase in the number of cervical cancer cases and deaths resulting from late detection is the motivation behind this study. This study aims to develop a model that helps women calculate the risk of cervical cancer based on their demographic information and medical history. The dataset used in this study was from Hospital University de Carcus and was obtained from the UC Irvin Repository. The dataset consists of demographic information, living habits, and medical history of 858 patients. Object-oriented analysis and Design methodology was adopted in this study for modularity and system design. A pipeline was implemented to build a composite classifier as a chain of transformer, sampler, and estimator, aiming to prevent overfitting, data leakage, and enhance the proposed model's performance. To build the composite classifier, StandardScaler was used as a transformer, SmoteTomek as the sampler, and XGBoost ensemble learning classifier as an estimator. A conventional XGBoost classifier was trained to identify the top 12 features that impacted the performance of the classification model. Performance metrics, including recall, accuracy, precision, and F1-score, were used to evaluate the model's performance. The proposed model correctly identifies 100% of women at risk of developing cervical cancer with an accuracy, precision, and recall of 99%, 89%, 100%, and 94% respectively. Based on the developed classification model and its respective results, the proposed model, which consists of a hybrid sampling technique of SmoteTomek with the XGBoost ensemble learning classifier as an estimator in a pipeline, demonstrates a significant improvement in identifying women at risk of developing cervical cancer, thereby tremendously reducing type II error, which occurred due to misclassification.

INTRODUCTION

According to Hansbauer [1], identifying the disease responsible for a person's symptoms is referred to as disease diagnosis. One of the most challenging aspects of this process is that certain signs and symptoms can be non-specific. Proper diagnosis is the first and most crucial step in treating any condition. Machine learning is a field that can help predict the presence of diseases by analyzing past training data [2].

One of the leading health problems among women across the globe, especially in developing countries, over the decades, is cervical cancer. Cervical cancer is a type of cancer that starts in the cervix. It can be fatal as it does not show symptoms in its early stages. Symptoms usually appear in late stages, when it could have spread to other organs [3]. When cervical cancer is discovered early, it is typically treatable and curable. Symptoms usually appear in late stages, when it could have spread to other organs like bones, liver, lymph nodes, and lungs [4]. The high increase in the number of cervical cancer cases and deaths resulting from late detection is the motivation behind this research study because early detection of cervical cancer helps save lives.

According to the Mayo Clinic, the primary cause of cervical cancer is the Human Papillomavirus (HPV), which is transmitted through sexual intercourse; other risk factors that lead to the development of cervical cancer include smoking, birth control pills (oral contraceptives), medicines that contain hormones, and the number of pregnancies. These factors and other variables are combined and evaluated in this research to predict whether a woman is at risk of developing cervical cancer.

According to statistics released by the World Health Organization [5], after breast cancer, cervical cancer is the second deadliest health challenge among women, with approximately 270,000 women dying from cervical cancer every year, with over 85% of these deaths occurring in developing countries. In Nigeria, cervical cancer accounted for 67.8% and 77% of genital tract malignancies in Sokoto and Zaria, respectively. Cervical cancer is the second most common cancer affecting women in Nigeria and the fourth most common cancer among women globally. [5]. There are an estimated 444,500 new cases of cervical cancer annually [6]. In 2022, an estimated 604,237 women were diagnosed with cervical cancer globally, accounting for 6.5% of all female cancers. Cervical cancer is the most common cancer among women in 36 low- and middle-income countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa [7].

The huge increase in the number of cancer patients across the globe has become a great challenge to medical sciences. As a result of technological advancements in recent years, medical sciences are combined with artificial intelligence to improve medicine. The introduction of modern computing technologies has played a vital role in the medical field and disease diagnosis, which has led to a tremendous reduction in human errors and helped in faster results.

Nowadays, machine learning algorithms have become very important in the medical sector, especially for diagnosing diseases from medical databases [8]. Many companies are using these techniques to predict diseases early and enhance medical diagnosis.

This study presents, an improved and robust model in terms of performance and overall accuracy to predict whether a woman is at risk of developing cervical cancer, since early detection of the disease will result in a reduction in its mortality rates.

This study combined XGBoost algorithm with the SmoteTomek hybrid data resampling algorithm and other data processing techniques, such as Standard Scaler, to build a pipeline known as a composite classifier. We also employed the built-in gain importance feature selection technique of the XGBoost classifier to identify the most significant features affecting the performance of our model for predicting cervical cancer risk. This approach focuses on the variables that improve predictive accuracy, enhancing the model's efficiency and interpretability for more accurate screening and diagnosis insights.

2. RELATED WORKS

The review of related works provides a concise overview of existing research on machine learning techniques for detecting cervical cancer and other relevant studies related to the techniques employed in this study. The review also narrates the various algorithms and approaches used.

Lu et al. [9] proposed a voting ensemble strategy to predict the risk of cervical cancer. A filling technique with a correction mechanism was adopted to address missing values. Logistic regression, decision tree, support vector machine, multilayer perception, and k-nearest neighbour were used for the voting strategy with grid search. The performance measure was based on accuracy, recall, precision, and F1 score. The result of the study showed that the proposed voting method had an accuracy of 83.16%, a recall of 28.38%, a precision of 51.75%, and an F1 score of 32.80%. However, their result can be improved for better performance.

In their study, Nithya and Ilango [10] applied machine learning techniques using R to analyze the risk factors associated with cervical cancer. The research focused on various feature selection methods to identify key attributes for predicting cervical cancer. Significant features were identified using different selection techniques through multiple iterations of model training. This process ultimately resulted in the development of an optimized feature selection model. Additionally, classifier models were constructed using algorithms such as C5.0, random forest, rpart, K-nearest neighbours (KNN), and support vector machines (SVM). The study thoroughly examined the possibilities for training and evaluating the models' performance. The results of their study showed that C5.0 and random forest classifiers have performed reasonably well with comprehensive accuracy in identifying women exhibiting clinical signs of cervical cancer.

Islam et al. [11] used classification and association data mining techniques to predict cervical cancer. Their dataset was tested on Logistic Model Tree (LMT), Decision Tree, Artificial Neural Network (ANN), and Random Forest classifiers were utilized. K-fold cross-validation was employed to divide the dataset. The association process was used to find strongly connected attributes in the dataset. The result of the study showed that the Random Forest classifier has the best recall, while the classifier with the lowest accuracy is an artificial neural network. Other performance evaluation metrics used in the study are precision, F1-score, and kappa. The author, however, does not specify how he dealt with the imbalanced nature of the dataset.

In a study by Fang et al. [12], a comparison study was conducted between the autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model and the Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) model to determine which was more accurate for forecasting the occurrence of COVID-19 in the USA. Three accuracy metrics were used to evaluate the performance of the two models:

mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square error (RMSE), and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). For both the training and validation sets, the MAE, RMSE, and MAPE values for the XGBoost model were lower than those for the ARIMA model. Their results showed that the XGBoost model could help improve the prediction of COVID-19 cases in the USA over the ARIMA model.

Angara et al. [13] proposed a semi-supervised learning method for cervical cancer precancer detection. The authors used data from studies conducted by the US National Cancer Institute to train a convolutional Neural Network algorithm. Various data augmentation techniques were utilized in their work to solve specular reflection problems. They claimed that their approach brings significant performance improvement with 82.02% accuracy.

Srivastava et al. [14] proposed a hybrid Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) model with hyperparameter tuning to improve early detection, diagnosis, and risk reduction for liver disease. Their study utilized a dataset comprising 416 individuals with liver issues and 167 without such a history. The results showed that the chi-square automated interaction detection model achieved an accuracy of 71.36%, while the classification and regression trees model reached an accuracy of 73.24%. Both models significantly outperformed conventional methods.

Akter et al. [15] proposed three machine learning models, which include Decision Tree, Random Forest, and XGBoost, to identify cervical cancer from behaviour and its variables using the cervical cancer behaviour risk dataset. The dataset used in this study is minimal. It contains 72 records. Despite the small size of the dataset used in the study, no strategy was used to combat the problem of overfitting rather, the study used a split technique where 80% of the data was in the training set, and 20% of the data was in the testing set, this technique does not work perfectly on small dataset especially when using decision tree and random forest classifier. The technique used for feature selection in this study is not correctly stated. The outcome of their study showed that the Random Forest and Decision Tree classifiers achieved an accuracy of 93.33%; however, there were also misclassifications, despite the models achieving an accuracy of 93.3%, respectively.

Kumar [16] explored a range of predictive models on the breast cancer Wisconsin dataset. They developed an ensemble model utilizing several algorithms, including k-nearest neighbours, random forest, logistic regression, support vector machine, decision tree, AdaBoostM1, gradient boosting, stochastic gradient boosting, XGBoost classifier, and CatBoost. The model's performance was evaluated using recall, precision, and F-measure metrics. The proposed model achieved a maximum accuracy of 99.45%.

Kanitkar et al. [17] developed a system that used demographic data to detect whether a patient has a cervical abnormality. They compared the performance of ten different ML algorithms. The authors used Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Tree, Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), Voting Classifier, and Ada Boost. SVM with PCA (Principal Component Analysis) and RFE were used to extract highly correlated risk factors successfully. The results of their binary classification in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score showed that the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) performed better than other algorithms with an accuracy of 75%, precision of 0.78, recall of 0.74, and F1-score of 0.75, respectively; however, it does not specify how it dealt with the imbalanced nature of the dataset.

Umesh et al. [18] proposed a mathematical machine learning method-based model, Boruta with SVM, to analyze various possibilities of cervical cancer. However, the research utilized Random Forest, SVM, decision tree, and Boruta to build different classification models. The Boruta method was designed to represent all significant features within the classification model. Their results showed that Boruta analysis with SVM performed reasonably well, with precision, recall, and F1-score values of 0.912, 0.891, 0.798, and 0.768, respectively.

Rahman et al. [19] proposed a classification model that can diagnose cervical cancer by combining the predictions of three classifiers: Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, and Random Forest. The voting technique was used with Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, and Random Forest. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) helped reduce dimensions, while the SMOTE technique was applied to balance the cervical cancer dataset obtained from the UCI Machine Learning Repository. Their study showed that balancing the dataset with SMOTE improved the model's performance.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The framework for this study is divided into various components, as shown in the system's architecture in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Architecture of the Cervical Cancer Risk Prediction Model

3.1 Dataset

The cervical cancer risk factor dataset used in this study is from Hospital University de Carcus and was obtained from the UC Irvin Repository. The raw data is the real electronic health record of patients. It contains 858 cases (patients). All instances of the dataset have 36 features, including the target variables. The target variables are the decision-makers that confirm

whether the person is diagnosed with cervical (1) or not (0). The dataset contains various patient attributes, including demographic data, sexual behaviour, smoking habits, contraceptive usage, history of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs), and diagnostic outcomes related to cervical cancer. The proposed model is trained to learn how to efficiently match the independent variables with the target variable to predict if a woman is at risk of developing cervical cancer or not.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

There are a lot of missing values in the dataset due to patients not given answers to certain private questions. If the missing values/data in the dataset are not handled properly, we might build a biased model, which can lead to incorrect results. Hence, we adopted two techniques for handling missing values: these techniques are;

3.2.1 Dropping Technique

This technique deletes rows or columns with missing data; if any columns have more than half of their values as null, the entire column can be deleted. In the same way, rows can also be dropped if they have one or more null column values. Due to the size of the dataset, instead of dropping all the columns with missing values, we dropped only the two columns with 91.72% missing values. Then we used the imputation method to handle the remaining missing values.

3.2.2 Imputation Method

Missing value Imputation, or replacement techniques, assist machine learning models in learning from incomplete data. This approach is utilized in this study because removing data from the dataset each time is not practical and can significantly reduce the dataset's size. Such a reduction raises concerns about bias and can lead to inaccurate analysis. After dropping the two columns with more than 90% missing values, we used the imputation method (replacing missing data with mean values) to handle the rest of the missing values because our dataset size is not very big, and removing many parts of it can have a significant impact on the final model.

The final stage of the data cleaning is to remove features that are highly correlated with each other and also those that have no or very low correlation with the target variable (Biopsy). To do this, we perform exploratory data analysis on the dataset using the Pearson correlation Matrix.

3.2.3 Pearson correlation for the feature selection step

The steps involved in using Pearson correlation for feature selection are as follows;

Step 1: We set an absolute value of 0.7 as the threshold for selecting the variables. If the features are correlated, we drop the feature with a lower correlation coefficient value than the target variable.

Step 2: We read the CSV file 'risk_factor_cervical_cancer.csv' located in the 'drive' directory and assign it to the DataFrame, cervical_data using the read_csv() function.

Step3: we create a correlation Matrix of the dataset; corr_matrix = cervical_data.corr()

$$\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i) \quad 2$$

standard deviation:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2} \quad 3$$

Using this formula, we replaced all the input values with the Z-score for every value. Hence, we get values ranging from -1 to +1, keeping the range intact.

Standardization performs the following:

- Converts the Mean (μ) to 0
- Converts the S.D. (σ) to 1

3.5 Feature Selection Process

The XGboost feature importance ranking was used to identify the most relevant features in the dataset, which can be used to train the proposed model to best identify women at risk of developing cervical cancer. The performance measure used for feature importance ranking in this study is the Gini index. when training a tree, it is possible to compute how much each feature decreases the impurity. The more a feature decreases the impurity, the more important the feature

3.6 Resampling Process

This research study adopted a hybrid approach to handle class imbalance. A resampling technique known as SmoteTomek was used to handle the class imbalance, as 93.6% of the target variable belongs to the majority class, while 6.4% belongs to the minority class. Figure 3 shows the distribution of the target variable. Training the proposed model without handling class imbalance may lead to learning how to predict the majority class, and failing to learn how to predict the minority class, which is more important for this research study.

Figure 3 Target Variable Distribution

4. BUILDING THE COMPOSITE CLASSIFIER

To avoid the problem of overfitting caused by data leakage, a composite classifier (pipeline) was constructed to combine several components during model building. The components include data resampling, data transformation, model training, and hyperparameter tuning. The process of building the composite classifier is as follows:

Step 1. The training set was randomly divided into five folds, of which four folds were used as the training set and one-fold was used as the validation set.

Step 2. StandardScaler was used to convert the features to the same scale

Step 3. Synthetic minority oversampling technique with TomekLink (SMOTETomek) was used to conduct imbalanced data processing for each training set.

Step 4. Defined the hyperparametric search space and used a random-search algorithm with 5-fold cross-validation to determine the best combination of parameters for each model.

Step 5. The best combination of parameters was applied to the algorithm, and its effectiveness was evaluated on a test set.

5. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed model was implemented in an Anaconda 3 environment using Jupyter Notebook with Python 3.9.11. Scikit-learn was used for data manipulation with Pandas, data visualization using Matplotlib and Seaborn, mathematical operations/array processing using Numpy, and also for implementing the XGBoost algorithm. The model was deployed into production using Flask.

5.1 User Interface Implementation

We developed a user interface that asks users to answer questions about their living habits, demographic information, and medical history. Once the user enters the information using the interface, it is passed to the Flask webserver, which is then forwarded to the model at the backend.

The user interface content was structured and styled using HTML and CSS, with JavaScript to add interactivity.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We have implemented a conventional XGBoost classifier as a base model and an XGBoost classifier as an estimator in a pipeline. The performance of the proposed model is based on accuracy (Acc), precision (Pre), recall (Rec), and F1-score as shown in the classification reports. The results obtained on the available data showed that by the application of the conventional XGBoost model in the prediction of cervical cancer risk, an accuracy value of 93% was obtained, while for the proposed model based on XGBoost as an estimator in a pipeline, an accuracy of 99% was obtained. From the confusion matrix shown in Figures 4 and 5 that compares the conventional XGBoost model used in the existing system with the proposed model based on pipeline, we can see how the existing model suffered from huge misclassification (False Negative; Type II Error) despite having an accuracy of 93%. Implementing the pipeline drastically reduces this misclassification in the proposed system. We also generate the classification report to evaluate the performance of the proposed system. From the statistics

obtained from the classification reports, it is possible to get other statistically significant information, such as recall, precision, and F1 values, as presented in Table 1

Table 1: Classification Report of the Conventional XGboost Classifier

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.96	0.97	0.96	164
1	0.17	0.12	0.14	8
Accuracy			0.93	172
Macro avg	0.56	0.55	0.55	172
Weighted avg	0.92	0.93	0.93	172

Figure 4: Confusion Matrix of the Conventional XGboost Classifier

In Table 4.1, the first metric is the precision, the precision is a measure of the ratio between the number of correct classifications of a given class on the total number of times that the algorithm classifies it. The recall metric expresses the sensitivity of the model and is represented by the ratio between the correct classifications for a given class on the total number of cases in which the event occurs. Based on these definitions, we can see that for the positive class, the conventional XGBoost model is not sensitive and precise in recognizing instances that present women who are at risk of cervical cancer. In predicting cervical cancer risk, the precision and the recall values obtained for the positive class are 0.17 and 0.12 (17% and 12%), respectively. For the negative class, an accuracy of 0.93, precision of 0.96, and recall of 0.97 (93%, 96%, and 97%) were obtained. These results showed that the existing system was able to identify only 21% of the positive class, which represents women at risk of cervical cancer. At the same time, for the proposed model, a binary classifier based on a pipeline, the model is sensitive and precise in recognizing instances that present women who are at risk of developing cervical cancer with

accuracy, precision, and recall of 0.99, 0.89, and 1.00 (99%, 89%, and 100%), respectively. This means that on average, out of 172 cases used to evaluate the performance of the proposed model, the model correctly classifies all the patients who are at risk of developing cervical cancer. The proposed method for the classification of cervical cancer risk is robust and provides significant performance. With the results obtained from this study, the proposed system served as a significant tool to support clinical decisions in the prevention of cervical cancer. Figure 4.13 shows the confusion matrix of the proposed system between 0 and 1, representative of the classification capacity of the proposed system. It showed that out of 164 negative cases, the proposed system was able to identify 163 negative cases (True Negative = 163), and misclassified 1 case as positive (False Positive = 1). This showed that 99% of the negative cases were correctly identified. Likewise, out of 8 positive cases, the proposed system was able to identify all 8 positive cases (True Positive = 8), and no positive cases were misclassified (False Negative = 0). The results showed that the proposed system was able to identify 99% of the negative cases and 100% of the positive cases.

Table 2: Classification Report of the Proposed System

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	1.00	0.99	1.00	164
1	0.89	1.00	0.94	8
Accuracy			0.99	172
Macro avg	0.94	1.00	0.97	172
Weighted avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	172

7. MODEL DEPLOYMENT

The model was deployed into production using a Flask API. The results of the deployed model for predicting women who are at risk of developing cervical cancer and women who have a low

risk of cervical cancer are shown in Figures 5, 6, and 7, respectively.

Figure 5: Prediction Page of the Cervical Cancer Risk Prediction Model

Figure 6: Result Page of the Cervical Cancer Risk Prediction Model

Figure 7: Result Page of the Cervical Cancer Risk Prediction Model

8. CONCLUSION

In the field of medical healthcare, early detection of cervical cancer remains challenging due to its asymptomatic nature. Based on the developed classification model and respective results, it can be concluded that this study has successfully achieved all the objectives set in section 1.3 for the problem of detecting cervical cancer. This study proposes a hybrid approach using a composite classifier that integrates diverse algorithms and techniques in a pipeline to predict the risk of developing cervical cancer. The hybrid approach leverages SMOTETomek for data resampling, XGboost for feature selection and classification, achieving better accuracy and optimal performance than the existing system. The model performed better than the existing model on all evaluation metrics by correctly identifying 100% of the total positive cases. (Recall = 1.0, i.e., 100%), and an accuracy score of 0.99, i.e., 99% which indicates that the model can correctly identify 100% of women who are at risk of developing cervical cancer.

The model performed well in predicting women at risk of developing cervical cancer based on demographic and behavioral data.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

The attained results indicate that the proposed system successfully addresses the problem of cervical cancer detection. The key recommendations of this solution are for the potential cervical cancer patients as well as the entire healthcare industry. By earlier identification of the patients at risk of cervical cancer, the proposed system can help save lives and can also reduce the mortality rate of cervical cancer. The proposed system has the potential to open a new prospect for medical and healthcare institutions as they can address cervical cancer disease proactively before its occurrence.

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